

A Thematic Analysis of Learning Experiences of MAPEH Major Students with Perceived Sensory Processing Challenges

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ABSTRACT: In the Philippines, students of Bachelor of Science in Secondary Education (BSEd) major in Music, Arts, Physical Education & Health (MAPEH) struggle to improve the characteristics of being competent, knowledgeable and versatile on all four areas of MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education & Health) demanded by the program. This research analyzes the feelings and insights of MAPEH students with suspected sensory processing challenges in their learning experiences required by the program. The research is qualitative in nature and employed in-depth interview and thematic analysis as methods in order to explore the learning experiences of the participants with suspected sensory processing challenges. The research concludes that the MAPEH students with suspected sensory processing challenges perceived that their learning experiences are mixtures of Struggles, Power of choice, Scaffolding, and Motivation. This research provides better insights and understanding for MAPEH students with sensory processing challenges to enhance, increase and transform their skills in a higher level of learning.

KEYWORDS: suspected sensory processing challenges, suspected sensory integration disorders, learning experiences in MAPEH

INTRODUCTION

Sensory processing also referred to as sensory integration refers to how the sensory information and stimuli from the body and the environment is processed, integrated, and organized to generate an appropriate behavioural response (Jones, *et.al.* 2020, SIE, 2023). Sensory stimuli are classified into two types which are the special senses (vision, hearing, smell taste, and vestibular function- sense of balance and spatial orientation) and general senses (touch, pain, temperature, pressure, vibration, and proprioception- sense of relative position of body parts in space) (Dharani, 2015).

Describing typical sensory processing development, defining sensory processing dysfunction, and guiding intervention programs are guided by Ayres' Sensory Integration Theory, introduced by Dr. A. Jean Ayres in the 1970s. Ayres believed that intersensory integration, the ability to coordinate sensory information from various stimuli and various modalities, permits more flexible and adaptive behaviour in a complex environment. Also, it is the foundation to function while sensory integration dysfunction leads to challenges in development, learning and emotional regulation. More than this, he hypothesized that sensory processing impairments lead to decreased motivation, poor stimulus registration and reduced sensory modulation (Guardado & Sergent, 2023).

In support of Ayre's Sensory Integration Theory, Dunn's model can be used as a framework to analyze how individuals process sensory information. With this, they reported that university students commonly experience sensory overload and sensory-seeking behaviour. Sensory overload can lead to anxiety, stress, and fatigue which can negatively impact academic performance and social interaction. While sensory-seeking behaviour such as fidgeting or tapping their feet can distract others and negatively impact social interaction as well. Four themes were determined from the lived experiences of people with sensory processing challenges: 1) physical and social environment, 2) experiences of the transition and adjustments from high school to college, 3) the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic, and 4) sensory preferences (Ghanbari *et.al.* 2025).

On the other hand, Keles (2025) studied the relationship between sensory profile and academic achievement among university students. Using the Dunn's sensory model, the students were classified in the "low registration", "sensory sensitivity", and "sensation avoidance". Result shows that these students demonstrate significantly lower academic performance than their peers. While Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) suggests how guided support and peer collaboration can help learners with processing difficulties (Ebadi *et.al.* 2010). Understanding how these affect learning, movement, behaviour is relevant especially for adult learners in multidisciplinary courses such as MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) education.

In the Philippines, MAPEH education is one of the specializations/ majors in the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) program which is a highly demanding program that requires mastery across the four disciplines- Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health. This program aims to develop learner's physical fitness, creativity, critical thinking, and social skills (Ched Memorandum Order, Section 4 ,Series of 2004). With the multidisciplinary nature of this specialization, it demands adept cognitive and psychomotor competency, making it more difficult for learners with sensory processing challenges. While some learners have innate talents related

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to this specialization like singing, dancing, and in sports others may experience difficulties performing these activities due to challenges in sensory processing (Critz et.al. 2015). In some Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) like Philippine Normal University (PNU), they integrated screening processes through singing and dancing auditions in addition to their curriculum as part of MAPEH student selection criteria (PNU Manual of Operation, 2015). However, in other HEIs like Saint Louis University there are no special screening or assessment for students taking up BSEd major in MAPEH, in which students may experience learning difficulties along their academic journey.

Sensory processing has been studied focusing on early childhood and special education context. However, despite the relevance of this topic in the MAPEH education, there is very limited existing literature on how sensory processing challenges affect the experiences of adult learners particularly in performance-based programs.

To address this gap, this study explored the learning experiences of BSEd MAPEH majors with perceived sensory processing challenges focusing on determining the areas of difficulties and perception of students towards their peers having sensory processing challenges as a guide in the improvement of MAPEH course learning experiences.

Significance of the Study

This study highlights various significance across areas. Generally it contributes to the limited study and addresses the gap on sensory processing challenges and learning experiences among adult learners specifically in performance-based education courses like MAPEH.

For MAPEH students, this study would provide them with a deeper understanding of the challenges and experiences of students with sensory processing issues. Through which students, not just those who're facing such challenges, are empowered to learn appropriate strategies to fulfill the demands of the course and seek appropriate academic support.

For educators, student-teachers, and higher education institutions, the study underscores the importance of comprehensive learning strategies to accommodate learners with sensory processing challenges which may lead to informed curriculum design fostering an inclusive learning environment.

For researchers, this serves as a foundation for deeper study on sensory processing challenges in higher education preceding the creation of proper interventions and policy development in the academe.

Statement of the Problem:

The study generally aims to understand the experiences and challenges encountered by MAPEH major students towards the course. Specifically it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the experience of students towards MAPEH as a major?
 - 1.1. What is the disposition of MAPEH major students on the difficulty of their courses?
2. What are the competency skills/ tasks in the MAPEH major that students find difficult?
3. How do MAPEH major students express their difficulties and challenges encountered in their program?
4. What is the viewpoint of MAPEH majors towards their peers experiencing difficulties in performing their tasks/ competency in various MAPEH courses?

How are the Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH) learning experiences perceived by the MAPEH students with suspected sensory processing challenges?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed mix method research. Quantitative using a survey questionnaire in checklist form was employed to determine the 1.) profile of the respondents, 2.) to determine the areas of difficulties in the MAPEH program and 3.) to identify students who have sensory processing disorder. The data gathered was analyzed using frequency counts and percentages. Qualitative research utilizing in-depth interviews was conducted to have a deeper understanding of the experiences and difficulties dealt by students who are suspected with sensory processing challenges (Boyce & Neale; 2006; Gray DE, 2009). Cool and warm analysis was implemented to the responses gathered through the interview. Cool analysis was applied to identify the significant statements or verbalizations of each participant. Such statements served as the basis in the conduct of the warm analysis stage where data categories were formulated and themes evolved.

Locale and Population Subjects of the Study

The focus of this study were MAPEH major students with suspected sensory processing challenges at the School of Teacher Education and Liberal Arts (STELA), Saint Louis University (SLU), Baguio City.

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The respondents were chosen through purposive sampling, specifically criterion sampling. Criterion was set to identify individuals having to be suspected to have sensory processing challenges. The researcher with the aid of professional education professors chose the participants based on the following following criteria: (a) currently enrolled in SLU as MAPEH major students (at least 3rd year level); (b) recommendation of MAPEH students with suspected sensory processing challenges from the faculty of MAPEH; and d) categorized as students with Suspected Sensory Processing Challenges (SPC) as suggested by results of the checklist “Sensory Modulation (Adult SPD Symptoms -Ages 18+)” which was conceptualized by Dan Travis (2011). Selected students who were classified based on the criteria were recruited to participate in an in-depth interview (Van Maanen, 1992; Boyce, Neale, 2006).

Instrumentation and Data Collection Procedure

To understand the learning experiences of MAPEH major students, the researchers handed out robotfoto (refer to appendix B) to determine the profile of the participants then conducted self-evaluation adopting the Sensory Modulation (*Adult SPD Symptoms -Ages 18+*) checklist conceptualized by Dan Travis (2011) (refer to appendix C) to further determine students who are suspected to have a processing challenges. Interview questions were crafted based on the problem this research sought to explore.

Prior to the conduct of study, a letter of request was handed to the Dean of School of Teacher Education and Liberal Arts for approval. MAPEH majors were then oriented with the purpose and background of this study together with the consent to participate in the study.

A two-stage data collection was carried out in this study. In the first stage, robotfoto was personally completed by the respondents for profiling using robotfoto which includes their academic background and the challenges encountered in coping up with the essential skills/ performance in their respective Major courses. Using the robotfoto, the research selected students who would undergo the self-evaluation with the use of *Sensory Modulation (Adult SPD Symptoms -Ages 18+)* checklist to identify the final set of respondents.

The second stage was the in-depth one-on-one interview. Prior to the conduct of the interview, aide memoire (refer to appendix A) was given to the respondents containing letters to the respondents and consent. The interview was facilitated using the following guide questions:

1. How do you feel being a MAPEH major student?
2. Do you think the MAPEH major is difficult?
3. Do you feel any difficulty in performing your tasks/competency skills as MAPEH majors (like in dances, choral singing, swimming, gymnastics, etc..?)
4. How do you verbalize your difficulty and feelings in pursuing your course?
5. How do the other MAPEH students feel about those who have difficulty in

performing their tasks/competency skills in their different MAPEH subjects?

The data gathered all throughout the study were treated with utmost confidentiality and in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Audio recordings were carried out with the consent of the participants.

Analysis of Data

The academic profile together with the self-evaluation of the respondents were analyzed using frequency and percentage. The results of the sensory modulation checklist were subjected to simple frequency counts to determine the number of responses per criteria. The data gathered in the in-depth interview were treated using the cool and warm analysis. Preceding that, audio recordings were transcribed individually. The texts were subjected to phenomenological reduction. Cool and warm analyses were observed in the study after the grids were contrasted. The cool analysis segment included the identification of the significant statements or verbalization of each participant. The statement served as the basis in the conduct of a warm analysis segment where the data categories were formulated and themes were evolved.

Throughout the process, researchers observed constant vigilance through reading and re-reading the significant statement in order to facilitate the surfacing of the essence of the phenomenon.

Correspondence technique was utilized to further determine the subjects for which the theme will emerge in this study for member checking procedure (Lincoln & Guba, as cited in the Guzman & Guillermo, 2007). Furthermore, each of the participants was individually consulted to verify the consistency of the transcription and interpretation. This procedure assured the credibility and veracity of the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initial respondents were:

Experience of students towards MAPEH as Major

Difficult Competency Skills and Task in MAPEH program as Perceived by the Students
Expressions of Difficulties and Challenges Dealt by MAPEH Major Students
Perception of MAPEH Majors Towards Peers Experiencing Sensory Processing Challenge
Data Interpretation

From the total of thirty-one (31) students of MAPEH majors who participated in filling up our robotfoto, twenty-six (26) or 83.87% of them had passed all the major subjects in MAPEH while five (5) or 16.12% of them have not yet taken up some of the MAPEH subjects. Thirty (30) or 96.77% of the total population encountered difficulties in learning MAPEH skills. Only one (1) or 3.22% of them doesn't find it difficult or challenging. On the other hand, twentyfour (24) or 77.42% of the total population had two (2) or more problem in coping up with the essential skills/performances in MAPEH while seven 7 or 22.59% of them do not encounter any problems in coping with the essential skills/performances in MAPEH.

Table 1.1		
Variables		
Total Number of Students		
Students Completed		
Taking Course	Profile of MAPEH Major Students	Percent (%)
Not yet taking some of the Subjects	Count	100%
	31	83.87%
	26	16.12%

Table 1.2		
Profile of		
Encountered difficulties in learning MAPEH		
MAPEH Major Students		
Variables	Count	Percent (%)
Encountered difficulties in learning MAPEH	30	96.77%
doesn't find difficult or challenging	1	3.22%
Has two (2) or more problem in coping up with the essential skills/performances in MAPEH	24	77.42%
Do not encounter any problems in coping up with the essential skills/performances in MAPEH	7	22.59%

From the thirty (31) MAPEH students of STELA, six (6) or 19.35% of them were categorized as students with suspected sensory processing challenges. They were selected as the participants of the study based from the result of the checklist **"Sensory Modulation (Adult SPD Symptoms -Ages 18+)"** which was conceptualized by Dan Travis (2011). Through the checklist floated, the researchers determined individuals with sensory processing challenges by identifying results with a total of 29 items (30% of the entirety of the material) checked from the checklist. Among the six identified students with cases of suspected sensory processing challenges, the researcher tallied the number of checked items per category namely: *a.) General modulation, b.) Over-responsiveness, c.) Under-responsiveness, d.) Sensory Seeking, e.) Sensory Discrimination, f.) Sensory-based Motor Abilities, g.) Social and Emotional and h.) Internal Regulation* for each of the individuals. The results of the given checklist to the six (6) participants provided better insights on the profiling of the participants.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

As showed in our repertory grid of the study, the following themes discovered are struggles, scaffolding, motivation and power of choice. Each theme was discussed in this part comprehensively.

Table 2		
Profile of MAPEH Major Students		
Variables	Count	Percent (%)
Student with suspected sensory processing challenges	6	19.35%

Checklist		
General Modulation	6	100%
Over-Responsiveness	5	83.33%
Unger-Responsiveness	6	100%
Sensory Seeking	6	100%
Sensory Discrimination	6	100%
Sensory-Base Motor Abilities	5	83.33%
Social and Emotion	6	100%
Internal Regulation	6	100%

Figure 1: Perceptions of MAPEH students with suspected sensory processing challenges on their chosen course

Struggles

Nuzzi (2015) talks about the theory of Gardner, the Multiple Intelligence, which discusses the affirmation of an individual mental activities such as thinking, understanding, learning and remembering cannot be shown good enough in a single dimension like the IQ score.

Unique cognitive profile would be a better account of individual’s strength and weaknesses. MAPEH students with suspected sensory processing challenges faced difficulties in bodily kinesthetic, where in, they could hardly follow or remember basic steps in a dance. This finding is supplemented by the responses of the participants. (*I am not that good at dancing especially in following steps and choreography; I am having difficulty in performing dance.*). The participants also expressed their difficulties in executing the proper skills in sports as well as adhering with the proper rhythm of particular song. (*I do feel some difficulties especially when it comes to dancing and gymnastics, most on the sport stuff; there are some strokes that I can’t perform in swimming well but I am still trying; I can’t follow the proper rhythm of a particular song*). Parham & Mailloux (2015) reiterate the statement that individuals who have problem in integrating knowledge could hardly translate it into skills or performance. On the other hand, the participants signify their struggles because they have difficulties in verbalizing feelings and lack of interest to their chosen course. (*I keep telling myself that I don’t need others held; most on the sport stuff since I am not much of a sporty person*).

Ayres (2005) who formulates the Sensory Integrating Theory which talks about the different aspects and being aware and sensitive senses on the environment but being delayed in processing the messages in our brain supplements such finding of this study (Miller, 2009).

Scaffolding

MAPEH students with suspected sensory processing challenges often enthuse achievements in performing their essential skill through a major learning strategy known as scaffolding. Participants believe that through *peer teaching* they will fulfill their

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objectives. (*I'm asking help from them to overcome these difficulties that I have in this course; others helping the one who experience difficulty*). Such view is supported by Ebadi, Khatib, and Shabadi (2010) who reiterate the perspective of Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). This theory of ZPD formulates collaborative attempt, where learners learn and internalize new concepts and psychological skill (Ebadi, Khatib, & Shabadi, 2010). On the other hand, when collaboration happens in a learning environment, students with suspected sensory processing challenges overcome their difficulties in learning their essential skills. (*my classmates don't leave me instead they help to learn the aspects where I found it difficulty; helping each other to have a participation with each other to finish the task that was given*). Tomlinson (2010) reiterate that when corroborating by more knowledgeable peers who engage in thoughtful discussion they are assuring that every skill can be developed. This view is supplemented by Chen (2007) and Hammel (2001) by stating that mentors must be open minded; willing to explore new things, positive, flexible and willing to devote time and energy to MAPEH students with suspected sensory processing challenges.

Power of Choice

Evans (2014) describe power of choice as students who experience more choice and autonomy in how to approach their works are more motivated and productive (Eshel & Kohavi, 2003). Participants explain that they perform better and feel the sense of fulfilling if the task is something that they really choose to do. (*I am happy because this the course I chose; I really love MAPEH since the activities are so fun-filled; It's something that I really want in the future*). This perspective is supplemented by Cosden et al, (1995) who elaborate that students-chosen learning tasks result in better performance than teacher-chosen tasks. Students who are given choices around their learning activities exhibit fewer problem behaviors (Bennett et al., 2006).

Motivation

Participants express their motivation in achieving their goals as MAPEH students. (*you need to fight in order to finish the task they assign to you; you need to pursue the activities in order to finish it*). Participants view their learning experiences in their chosen course as somewhat challenging so they are driven to be more motivated either by internal rewards (*meeting a challenge*) or extrinsic rewards (*passing the subjects*). Hardre & Reeve (2003) explain that autonomy-supportive teacher practices have positive impact on student motivation and engagement.

CONCLUSION

MAPEH students do a lot of activities that needs to internalize power of choice, a dose of motivation and scaffolding from their peers. MAPEH students see their tasks as challenges that they need to overcome. Some MAPEH students with suspected sensory processing challenges (SPC) that learning involving significant experiences as primarily tool to achieve their objectives. Learners with SPC should always participate in a lot of activities in order for them to familiarize, learn and adapt skills, and afterwards be able to perform it. Peer teaching (Scaffolding) is a good strategy or students who are encountering difficulties to cope with their learning tasks. Peer teaching is recapitulated as scaffolding which is very essential to MAPEH students with sensory processing challenges. On the other hand, power of choice and great motivation make individuals with SPC very inspired and motivated to finish a task successfully and efficiently regardless of struggles and difficulties they would face in attaining their goals.

RECOMMENDATIONS

With the findings and conclusion the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. MAPEH students with sensory processing challenges can be guided by the important people (parents, mentors and classmates) so that they easily adapt the skills and performances of the different activities of the four areas of MAPEH. (Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health); and
2. To continually enhance the qualities of performance of the students with suspected sensory processing challenges, the learners should always have the capability and the positive attitude of pursuing their goals through an optimistic perspectives in life.

Appendix A.

Aide Memoire PREAMBLE

(Salutation) Good day to you, sir/ ma'am. I am _____. You can call me _____. I am currently enrolled at Saint Louis University. Presently, I am working on our paper entitled: "Exploring the Learning Experiences of MAPEH Students with Suspected Sensory Processing Challenges" (*Magandang araw po sir/ ma'am. Ako po si _____. Pwede niyo po akong tawagin na _____. Ako po ay kasalukuyan na nag-aaral sa Unibersidad ng San Luis. Sa ngayon po ay may ginagawa kaming pananaliksik na tungkol sa "Paggalugad sa Karanasan sa Pag-aaral ng mga Mag-aaral ng mga MAPEH na Hinihinalang may Paghamon sa Pagproseso sa kanilang Pandama".*)

(Purpose) As a vital part of this academic endeavour, I am inviting you for a one-to-one interview session that will capture your own experience of the said phenomenon. This activity will be audio-recorded and it will be conducted in the Filipino language. (*Bilang importanteng parte sa aming akademikong pagsisikap, iniimbitahan ko po kayo na magkaroon ng isahang interbyu sesyon*)

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para kunin ang inyong karanasan sa nasabing penomenon. Itong aktibidad na ito ay gagamit ng audio-rekorder kung saan ito po ay maisasalin sa Filipino na lenggwahe.)

(Motivation) Your participation in this study shall be helpful in understanding the cases of suspected sensory processing challenges. *(Sa inyong partisipasyon sa aming pananaliksik ay makakatulong sa pagintindi sa mga kaso ng Paggalugad sa Karanasan sa Pag-aaral ng mga Mag-aaral ng mga MAPEH na Hinihinalang may Paghamon sa Pagproproseso sa kanilang Pandama.)*

(Consent) Before we start, I would like to ask for your consent if you are willing to take part on this study. *(Bago natin simulan, gusto ko lang po na hingin ang inyong permiso kung gusto niyo po na maging parte sa aming pananaliksik.)*

(Time) This activity will only take a maximum of fifteen (15) minutes. Do you have any questions or concerns? Are you now ready to answer some questions? *(Sa aktibidad na ito ay tatagal po ng mahigit labing-limang minutos. May mga katanungan o inaalala? Kayo po ba ay handa na para sagutin ang mga katanungan.?)*

Appendix B.

S: _____ TERTIARY LEVEL (COLLEGE LEVEL)						
Note: Put Check (✓) for each						
Currently enrolled in SLU as MAPEH major students	Inclusive date	ALREADY DECIDED TO TAKE MAPEH MAJOR SINCE 1 ST YEAR HIGH SCHOOL.	Shifter from other courses to MAPEH	Inclusive date	Current year in MAPEH	Inclusive date
	MONTH/YR		MONTH/YR		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4th Year • 3rd Year • 2nd Year 	
Put check MAPEH Major subjects enrolled in last 3 years.				Problems encountered in coping up with the essential skills/performance in their respective Major subjects.		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAPEH 1 Foundations of MAPEH • MAPEH 2 Philippine and Asian Music • MAPEH 3 Anatomical, Mechanical and Physiological Bases of Movement • MAPEH 4 Gymnastics • MAPEH 5 Philippine Folk Dance • MAPEH 6A Instruments Playing 1 Solfeggio And Applied Piano, Guitar & Bamboo Flute • MAPEH 6B Instruments Playing 2 Pangkat Kawayan & Ethnic Ensembles • MAPEH 7 Methods and Strategies in Teaching MAPEH • MAPEH 8 Advanced Team Sports -Volleyball, Softball, Basketball • MAPEH 9 Aquatics - Swimming And Other Water Activities • MAPEH 10 Integrated Music Theory • MAPEH 11 International Folk Dance and Other Dance Forms • MAPEH 12 Music Literature -Western Music • MAPEH 13 Rondalla Playing Instrumentation • MAPEH 14 Athletics, Individual, Dual And Combative Sports 				<p>Music</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Music • Playing Piano • Playing Guitar • Paying Bandurria/Octavina • Playing Gong Ensembles <p>Physical Education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Folk Dance • Delay Movements • Following Steps per Figure • Gymnastics • Forward-roll • Backward-roll • Cartwheel • Handstand • Diving • Aquatics • Floating • Dog Paddle • Backstroke • Free-style • Diving 		

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAPEH 15 Coaching And Officiating of Sports Events, Dance Competitions and Music Activities • MAPEH 16 Organization And Management Of Mapeh Activities • MAPEH 17 Personal, Community, Environmental Health, Safety Education And First Aid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basketball • Dribbling • Passing • Receiving • Throwing • Shooting 	
<p>List down Subjects enrolled in MAPEH that you encountered difficulties in learning MAPEH skills.</p>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAPEH1 • MAPEH2 • MAPEH3 • MAPEH4 • MAPEH5 • MAPEH6 • MAPEH7 • MAPEH8 • MAPEH 9 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MAPEH10 • MAPEH11 • MAPEH12 • MAPEH13 • MAPEH14 • MAPEH15 • MAPEH16 • MAPEH17 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volleyball • Dig Pass • Set Pass • Spike • Under/Over Head Serve <p>Table Tennis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forehand Stroke • Backhand Stroke • Chop • Smash <p>Badminton</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Picking • Catching • Sma • Smash

Appendix C. Sensory Modulation Checklist

Instruction:
General Modulation
 _____ has great difficulty with transitions, be they major life changes or small everyday stuff (one activity to another, going from inside to outdoors, etc.)
 _____ becomes engrossed in one single activity for a long time and seems to tune out everything else
 _____ Very high or very low energy level
 _____ are resistant to change in daily life and surrounding environment

Over-Responsiveness
 _____ distressed by others touching; would rather be the "toucher" than the "touchee". May not like being hugged.
 _____ very sensitive to pain, especially as compared to others
 _____ become overstimulated or overaroused when people come to the house or when in crowded places
 _____ overly excited/aroused in group settings
 _____ avoids crowds and hides, disappears, or acts out when guests come over
 _____ easily distracted by auditory or visual stimuli
 _____ can not attend certain public events or places due to excessive noise
 _____ over reacts to loud noises, like sirens
 _____ fearful of heights

<p>Under-Responsiveness</p> <p>_____ may fail to recognize stimuli that most would find alerting or strong</p> <p>_____ lethargic, hard to get going, appears "lazy" and unmotivated</p> <p>_____ doesn't seem to get dizzy</p> <p>_____ might not catch self when falling or protect self from getting hurt; lacks reflexes</p> <p>_____ doesn't interact with peers or adults; is hard to engage, an observer and not a 'do'er</p> <p>_____ is the last to notice when a person enters the room, if they notice at all</p> <p>_____ difficulty waking up in the morning (may not even notice alarm clock)</p>
<p>Sensory Seeking</p> <p>_____ will often rock or sway body back and forth while seated or standing still</p> <p>_____ frequently tip chair on back two legs</p> <p>_____ restless when sitting through a lecture, presentation, or movie</p> <p>_____ constantly chews on things, sucks thumb, and/or grinds teeth</p> <p>_____ prefers foods with very strong tastes and flavors</p> <p>_____ constantly bites nails or fingers</p> <p>_____ bites lips or insides of cheeks</p> <p>_____ frequently shakes leg</p> <p>_____ cracks knuckles often</p> <p>_____ great difficulty settling down for sleep</p>
<p>Sensory Discrimination</p> <p>_____ can't identify objects by touch alone</p> <p>_____ difficulty finding things in a desk, bag, or pocket without looking</p> <p>_____ difficulty heating food to the correct temperature, feeling if it is too hot or too cold</p>
<p>_____ difficulty concentrating on or watching a movie/tv show when there is background noise or distractions</p> <p>_____ difficulty remembering or understanding what people are saying</p> <p>_____ difficulty following directions if given two or three at one time</p> <p>_____ can not complete concentrated tasks if noises present</p> <p>_____ talks too loud or too soft</p> <p>_____ difficulty with speech and articulation</p> <p>_____ bumps into things frequently</p> <p>_____ often pushes too hard on objects, accidentally breaking them</p> <p>_____ difficulty judging how much pressure to apply when doing tasks or picking something up</p> <p>_____ often reverses numbers and letters or process them backwards</p> <p>_____ difficulty telling time on an analogue clock</p> <p>_____ difficulty reading and understanding a map, bus schedule, directions _____ difficulty organizing and grouping things by categories, similarities, and/or differences</p> <p>_____ difficulty reading text on computer screens</p> <p>_____ difficulty lining up numbers correctly for math problems and/or balancing a checkbook</p>

<p>Sensory-Based Motor Abilities</p> <p>_____ has difficulty learning to ride a bike or other moving equipment</p> <p>_____ clumsy, uncoordinated, and accident prone</p> <p>_____ difficulty walking on uneven surfaces</p> <p>_____ difficulty with fine motor tasks, such as buttoning, zipping, tying, playing games with small parts, closing zip loc bags, etc.</p> <p>_____ confuses right and left sides</p> <p>_____ prefers sedentary tasks, avoiding sports or physical activities</p> <p>_____ difficulty with handwriting; hard to read, writes slowly, gets wrist cramps</p> <p>_____ frequently bumps into people and things</p> <p>_____ easily fatigued with physical tasks</p> <p>_____ frequently misses when putting objects on a table</p> <p>_____ has difficulty pouring drinks</p> <p>_____ frequently drops items</p> <p>_____ often hums or talks to self while concentrating on a task</p> <p>_____ significant difficulty learning to tie things (shoes, bags, etc.)</p> <p>_____ difficulty with motor tasks requiring several steps</p> <p>_____ difficulty learning new motor tasks (a new dance, sport or exercise activity, how to drive, etc.)</p> <p>_____ loses balance frequently, maybe even when standing still</p>
<p>Social and Emotional</p> <p>_____ dislikes changes in plans or routines, needing structure</p> <p>_____ often described as "stubborn", "defiant", or "uncooperative"</p> <p>_____ is very emotional and sensitive, may also be prone to crying</p> <p>_____ can't seem to finish anything</p> <p>_____ has difficulty making decisions</p> <p>_____ is seen as rigid, bossy, and controlling</p>
<p>_____ prefers solitary activities over group participation</p> <p>_____ is often impatient and/or impulsive</p> <p>_____ doesn't always register or understand social cues and non verbal language</p> <p>_____ difficulty with authority figures</p> <p>_____ trouble relating to and socializing with peers and colleagues</p> <p>_____ has difficulty accepting defeat or forgiving self</p> <p>_____ frequently gets angry or has moments of rage</p> <p>_____ easily frustrated</p> <p>_____ needs sameness and routines; needs to know what to expect</p> <p>_____ gets frequent panic or anxiety attacks</p> <p>_____ has many fears and/or phobias</p> <p>_____ OCD-type qualities; can't let foods touch each other on a plate, has to wear clothes a certain way, or other obsessions and compulsions. _____ is easily distractible and often unorganized</p> <p>_____ hates surprises</p> <p>_____ difficulty seeking out and maintaining relationships _____ avoids eye contact.</p>
<p>Internal Regulation</p> <p>_____ difficulty falling asleep or getting on a sleep schedule</p> <p>_____ heart rate issues, including: unnecessary speeding, not slowing down when at rest, or not speeding up for tasks that require a higher heart rate</p> <p>_____ respiration too fast or slow for the appropriate state of arousal</p> <p>_____ over or under sensitive to bowel and bladder sensations</p> <p>_____ over or under sensitive to the sensations of hunger and thirst</p> <p>_____ irregular, inconsistent bowel, bladder and appetite sensations</p> <p>_____ difficulty with temperature regulation of body</p>

Sensory Modulation (Adult SPD Symptoms (ages 18+) By: Dan Travis

Appendix D.

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I'm asking help from them to overcome these difficulties that I have in this course. 2. It may not be hard if you can do the task that the teacher ask you to do. 3. Others helping the one who experience difficulty. 	<p><i>Peer Teaching</i></p>	<p>SCAFFOLDING</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. My classmates don't leave me instead they help to learn the aspects where I found it difficult. 2. Since they help each other, they define ways so that my classmates can join and participate and also have fun together. 3. Helping each other to have a participation with each other to finish the task that was given. 	<p><i>Collaboration</i></p>	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. This the course that I chose for myself. 2. It's something that I really want to do in the future. 	<p><i>Passion</i></p>	<p>POWER OF CHOICE</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I am happy because this is the course I chose. 2. It's what I like and its fulfilling. 3. While playing sports, I can freely express my emotions that cause me stressed. 4. I really love MAPEH since the activities are so fun-filled. 	<p><i>Sense of Fulfilling</i></p>	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. You need to fight in order to finish the task they assign to you. 2. I really tried my best to do all these activities for me to pass this subjects. 	<p><i>Extrinsic</i></p>	<p>MOTIVATION</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. You need to pursue the activities in order to finish it. 	<p><i>Intrinsic</i></p>	

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